

Influence of Eco-Accounting System on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

The paper investigated Influence of Eco-accounting System on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State in terms of sales volume and profitability. Two research questions and two hypotheses testable at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The study adopted a correlational design. A census population of 341 registered small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State were used. The instrument was a self-developed questionnaire titled Influence of Eco-accounting System on the Performance of Small and Medium scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State. The instrument was validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University. Test re-test technique was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. This was done by administering the instrument to 20 small and medium scale enterprises owners outside the study area in Rivers State. The instrument was re-administered after two weeks to the same respondents. Pearson Product Moment Correlation tested the reliability of the instrument to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data was analyzed with percentages, frequencies, tables while t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation tested the hypotheses. The results showed positive perfect and positive strong correlations between the eco-accounting system and sales volume and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises. The study concluded that Eco-accounting system is needed by small and medium scale enterprises to enhance sales volume and profitability. The study recommended amongst others that entrepreneurs should conduct eco-accounting system to overcome business cessations.

Keywords: Influence, Eco-Accounting System, Performance, Small, Medium, Scale, Enterprises

Introduction

The Eco-accounting system is made up of environmental accounting system and ecological accounting system. It is a combining form of representing Environmental accounting system and Ecological Accounting system such as ecolaw, ecopolitics, ecosystem etc. The Eco-accounting system is concerned with providing information to assist entrepreneurs with performance appraisal, control, decision-making and reporting for enterprises to maximize and optimize profit. It is based on environmental and ecological concepts which measures and values economic benefits and liabilities of entities.

According to Frank (2003), Lei, Zhou and Wang (2014), Igbodo, Mary and Emuze (2017), Eco-accounting system is defined as the identification of resources use, measurement and communication of environmental costs, environmental liabilities, environmental benefits, effects of the natural environment on a company in monetary terms and measurement of the influence a company has on the environment in physical terms. The costs include costs of cleanup or remediation of contaminated sites, environmental fines, penalties and taxes, purchase of pollution

prevention technologies and waste management costs etc. Environmental accounting measures the effects of natural environment on a company in monetary terms, while ecological accounting measures the influence a company has on the environment in physical terms. It is a subset of accounting proper targeted at incorporating both economic and environmental information. In many ways, eco-accounting system helps to bring sustainable development, success and growth of day-to-day business goals. Eco-accounting system helps to improve business growth in many ways such as: identification and measurement of complete environmental remediation, quantify and address long term environmental consequences, create and control budgets, forecast revenues, track business expenses, monitor business financial profitability, evaluate business periodically to assess progress of business and appraise loans before borrowing, determination of success factors for business e.g. sales, expenditure controls, annual budget, identify and avoid unfavourable costs in business, match costs with benefits to know losses and profits of business, identify favourable business environment and location, identify favourable business opportunities to invest wisely, identify government adverse tax policies, identify and improved on quality of products in business, identify strengths, weaknesses and opportunities of the business areas to invest, identify exactly what it cost to deliver a service or product, help entrepreneur to monitor and implement budget of the business plan to the letter, lead entrepreneur to purchase materials that will minimize the cost etc.

Accounting is the process of collecting, summarizing, analyzing and reporting in monetary terms tailored made financial information to users and management showing the costs and benefits of pursuing each alternative course of action open to management (Eddy, 2009). The need for proper accounting of the enterprises environment is inevitable as every business objectives is to make profit. Accounting provides important information for internal and external stakeholders in an economic system

A system is a set of connected, interdependent, interrelated things or devices that operate and interact together. A system refers to an entity or organization, conceptual or physical which has interdependent, interconnected and interrelated parts (Charity, 2011). A system is an organized collection of parts that are highly integrated in order to accomplish an overall goal in the organization. It is a complex interrelated components or objects. The components or objects may be physical such as machines, raw materials and personnel. Abstract components or objects are part of a system for instance, profit, goals, sale quota, morale, and production standard (Imaga, in Charity, 2011).

Performance is the ability of an organization to utilize its resources efficiently and to generate outputs that are consistent with its goals and objectives and relevant for its clients and stakeholders (Charity, 2011). Organizational performance comprises the real output or results of an organization as measured against its goals and objectives and intended outputs.

Small and medium scale enterprises are the basis for many nations' economic growth and development all over the world. Small and medium enterprises contribute to employment creation, growth in gross domestic product and growth in export earnings. The concept of small and medium scale enterprises has no universally accepted definition. Its definition varies from author to author, agency to agency, body to body and country to country and even within sectors in countries based on employees, revenues or fixed assets.

Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (2017) defined small and medium on the following criteria: Small scale enterprises are business with ten to forty-nine people with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million naira, while a medium scale enterprises has fifty to

one hundred and ninety-nine employees with a year turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million naira. The study therefore seeks to investigate the influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Eco-accounting system is advantageous for both internal and external decision making by users. It provides useful information regarding decision making for well-structured production, value of investment, identification and analysis of environmental costs and benefits. It identifies, collect and analyses data about raw materials concerning environmental impact of the business in monetary and physical terms which leads to more informed decision making for performance of small and medium scale enterprises in terms of sales volume and profitability regarding the performance of an entity.

Over the years in Bayelsa State, the researcher has been experiencing a gradual decline of sales volume and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises that aggravated to cessation of businesses. Perhaps this is as a result of failure on the part of small and medium scale enterprises owners to conduct Eco-accounting system before commencing business operations for inadequate or no knowledge about the benefits of the influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in terms of sales volume and profitability. These small and medium scale enterprises established started well and were well patronized but are no more in operations. These entities include fast foods enterprises, boutiques, bakery production enterprises, transportation enterprises, supermarkets, information communication technology outfits, private schools etc. If this ugly trend is not averted no one can tell how the future and economy of the State and Nigeria will become soonest. It is against this background that the study seeks to investigate the influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State in terms of sales volume and profitability performance.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of Eco-accounting on sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.
2. Examine the influence of Eco-accounting on profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. How does Eco-accounting influence sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?
2. How does Eco-accounting influence profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between Eco-accounting system and sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant relationship between Eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Review of Empirical Studies

Eco-Accounting system is a combining form of representing Environmental accounting system and ecological accounting systems such as ecolaw, ecosystem, ecopolitics etc. Environmental accounting system is defined as a method of measuring in economic terms the performance of any type of organization in relation to the environment (Mirela, 2012). Ecological accounting on the other hand, according to Lei et al (2014), is the measurement of the influence a company has on the environment in physical terms. Eco-accounting system is the identification of resources use, measurement and communication of environmental costs, environmental liabilities, environmental benefits, effects of the natural environment on a company in monetary terms and measurement of the influence a company has on the environment in physical terms (Lei et al, 2014, and Igbod et al, 2017).

The concept of small and medium scale enterprises has no universally accepted definition. Its definition varies from country to country, agency to agency, body to body, and even within sectors in countries based on employees, revenues or fixed assets. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (2017) defined small and medium on the following criteria: Small scale enterprises are business with ten to forty-nine people with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million naira, while a medium scale enterprises has fifty to one hundred and ninety-nine employees with a year turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million naira. European Union Commission (2005) defined small enterprises as businesses with employment of fifty (50) people and asset and capital turnover of seven (7) to ten (10) million Naira only. While medium enterprises are businesses with employment of two hundred and fifty (250) persons with asset and capital turnover of forty (40) to fifty (50) million Naira only.

The Federal ministry of Commerce and Industry (2015) define small and medium enterprises as firms with a total investment (excluding cost of land but including capital) of up to N750,000 and paid employment of up to fifty person. The contributions of Small and medium scale enterprises has been recombined as critical to the development of an economy as they possess great potentials for employment generation, improvement of local technology, output diversification, development of indigenous entrepreneurship and forward integration with large scale industries (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2018).

According to (Margaret in Pac, 2015) small and medium scale enterprises are defined as business firms with asset base (including working capital but excluding costs of land) not exceeding seven hundred and fifty thousand naira (N750,000.00) only and cost of investment project below four hundred thousand naira (N400,000.00) only. Small and medium business enterprise contribute to export earnings, employment creation, gross domestic product, technological assimilation, value creation for locally sourced resources, serve as source of new and improve technology, new products and service, new market development and also help in educating and development of new entrepreneurs that could add more value to the economy (Adebisi, Alaneme and Ofuani, 2015), (Jabeen & Mahmood, 2014), (Keh, Ngguyen and Ng, 2007), (Samson, 2015), (Anigbogu, Onwuteaka, Edoko and Okoli, 2014), (Aziz & Yassin, 2010), (Oni & A, 2012), (Terungwa, 2011), (Onwukwe & Ifeanacho, 2011).

Globally, it is estimated that 95% of the businesses are SMEs and contributing up to 60% of employment in private sector of the economy (Ayagari, Memirguc-Kunt and Maksimovic, 2011). Consequently, the contributions of SMEs to GDP in Nigeria is low (at 46.54%), to employment (at 25%) and export (2.7%) compared to other countries like in Singapore (70% employment and 50% to GDP), Germany (79% to employment and 49% to GDP) and China (75% to employment and 60% to GDP). Sales volume is the number of units sold within a reporting period of time (Hassan, 2019). Sales volume performance is the increases in the volume of entity revenue generated by an entity over a specific time. Sales performance is an increase in price of commodities and sales of more commodities or goods and services.

According to Charles (2021) profit is an absolute number determined by the amount of income or revenue above or beyond the costs or expenses enterprise incur. It is calculated as total revenue minus total expenses and appears on the income statement of an enterprise. Profitability is the ability of an entity to produce return on an investment based on its resources in comparison with an alternative investment. Profitability is the measurement of company's profit efficiency. A firm can make profit but is not profitable.

From the review of literature, it was discovered that there is no primary focus on the influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium enterprises in terms of sales volume and profitability performance, and its effects on industrial growth in Nigeria, but researchers focused mainly on the contribution of industrial, economic growth and development. Also, the literature lacks research works on accounting concepts of Entity, Going concern and conventions of Objectivity, Fairness, Prudence, etc

Method

The study adopted correlational design which is a form of research design that finds out the extent of relationship between two or more variables, and data from such variables that are in ratio or interval scale scores to create the possibility for the scores to be correlated (Nwankwo, 2016). It is correlational as it will collect data and try to establish the relationship between Influence of Eco-accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises. There are three hundred and forty one registered small and medium scale enterprises operating in Bayelsa State according to the Bayelsa State Ministry of Trade, Industry and Investment source 2021. The population of the study consisted of the whole three hundred and forty one (341) small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa State. The owners/managers of these three hundred and forty one (341) registered small and medium scale enterprises were used as the population. The sample size of the study was three hundred and forty one (341) registered small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa State. The sample size of the study consisted of the whole three hundred and forty one (341) registered small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Since the census sample size was manageable there was no sampling technique used. The instrument for data collection for the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled "Influence of Eco-Accounting system on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (IESPSMSE) in Bayelsa State". The responses to the research questions were rated on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was divided into two sections: Section "A" of the instrument contains demographic data of respondents while Section "B" of the instrument contains thirty (30) questionnaire items that elicited useful information for the research questions and objectives. The research instrument was validated by the researchers' supervisor and two other experts of Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational

Foundations in the Faculty of Education in Niger Delta University. Their corrections were used to modify the questionnaire to enhance the content validity of the instrument. Therefore, the instrument was valid. The test re-test technique was used to establish the reliability of the instrument for the study. This was done by administering the instrument to twenty (20) small and medium scale enterprises owners outside the study area in Rivers State. The instrument was re-administered after two weeks to the same respondents. The data obtained were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Therefore, the instrument was reliable. The instrument for the research data collection was the questionnaire. Three hundred and forty one (341) questionnaire for data collection was personally distributed by the researcher with the help of two research assistants to the owners of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The questionnaire were retrieved after a day. Three hundred and fourteen (314) completed questionnaire were successfully retrieved from the respondents representing 92% while twenty seven (27) questionnaire were unretrieved representing 8%. The data collected were analyzed with frequency distribution, tables, and simple percentages. While t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) tool were employed to answer the research questions and test the corresponding hypotheses.

Formula for Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) is

$$r = \frac{N\Sigma XY - \Sigma X \Sigma Y}{\sqrt{\{N\Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2\} \{N\Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2\}}}$$

Where: ΣX = Sum of scores for one variable X,

ΣY = Sum of scores for the other variable Y,

ΣX^2 = Sum of squares of the scores for X,

ΣY^2 = Sum of square of the scores for Y,

ΣXY = Sum of the product of X and Y,

N = Number of pairs of scores or number of respondents.

Decision Rule

Decision was based on the strength and magnitude of relationship between variables (Dancey & Reidy in Nwankwo, 2016) and comparison of calculated Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) r-value and Probability value (p-value) of significance at the chosen alpha level of 0.05. When the calculated r-value was less than the chosen alpha level of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted. When the calculated r-value was greater than the chosen alpha level of 0.05 the null hypotheses was rejected.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Demographic Variables.

Table 1 Percentage Distribution of Respondents based on Educational Qualification

S/N	Educational Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Ph.D	3	0.96
2	M.Sc/M.Ed	11	3.50
3	B.Sc/HND	182	57.96
4	NCE/OND	26	8.28
5	WAEC/NECO	92	29.30
	Total	314	100%

Source: Field Survey Data, 2021

Table 1 results shows the distribution of respondents by educational qualification. The results shows that 3 respondents representing (0.96%) are Doctor of Philosophy degree holders, 11 respondents representing (3.50%) are Master’s degree holders, 182 respondents representing (57.96%) are Bachelor of Science and Higher National Diploma degree holders, 26 respondents representing (8.28%) are Nigerian Certificate in Education and Ordinary National Diploma degree holders, while 92 respondents representing (29.30%) were West African Examination Certificate and National Examination Council Results holders respectively.

Table 2 Percentage Distribution of Respondents based on Designation/Position in Enterprise

S/N	Position	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Owners	281	89.49
2	Managers	33	10.51
	Total	314	100%

Source: Field Survey Data, 2021

Table 2 results shows the distribution of respondents based on position in small and medium scale enterprises. The results revealed that 281 respondents representing (89.49%) were owners of the enterprises, while 33 respondents representing (10.51%) were managers respectively.

Research Question One

How does Eco-accounting system influence the sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises.

Variable	N	R	r ²	Remark
Eco-accounting system and Sales volume	314	.726	0.527	Positive Strong relationship

Source: Field Survey Data, 2021

Table 3 shows Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The

Table results reveals that 314 respondents' responses were analyzed. A correlation coefficient (r) of .726 was obtained, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises. The r^2 is 0.527, therefore the variation in sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is 0.527×100 is 52.7%. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 52.7%.

Research Question Two

How does Eco-accounting system influence the profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Table 4 Pearson Product moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between Eco-accounting system and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises

Variable	N	R	r^2	Remark
Eco-accounting system and Profitability	314	.800	0.64	Positive strong relationship

Source: Field Survey Data, 2021

Table 4 reveals Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The responses of 314 respondents were analyzed to obtain a correlation coefficient of .800, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive correlation coefficient implies that an increase in eco-accounting system results to an increase in profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of .800 profitability of small and medium scale enterprises implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase in profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The r^2 obtained is 0.64, therefore, the variation in profitability of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is 0.64×100 is 64%. This means that, the influence of eco-accounting system on profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 64%.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting system and the sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa States

Table 5 Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises.

Variable	N	Df	R	p-value or sig	Alpha level	Decision
Eco-accounting and Sales volume	314	312	.726	.000	0.05	Sig p<0.05

Table 5 reveals the test of significance of Pearson Product moment correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. It can be deduced from the Table an observed probability value (p-value) or sig of .000 at 0.05 level of significance with 312 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, ($r(312) = .726, p < 0.05$). Since the p-value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis of “There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting system and the sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State” is rejected. The alternative hypothesis is upheld. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting system and the sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Table 6: Test of significance of Pearson Product Moment correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises

Variable	N	Df	R	p-value or sig	Alpha level	Decision
Eco-accounting and Profitability	314	312	.800	.000	0.05	Sig p<0.05

Table 6 reveals the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. It can be discerned from the Table that, the observed probability value (p-value) or sig is .000 at 0.05 level of significance with 312 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, ($r(312) = .676, p < 0.05$). Since the p-value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis of “There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State” is rejected. The alternative hypothesis is upheld. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the analysis showed that all the purposes listed were agreed to be required and needed by both owners and managers of small and medium scale enterprises for successful operations in business in Bayelsa State. The Eco-accounting system has definitely promoted and increased performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State in terms of Sales volume and profitability. The findings of this study are as follows:

Research Question 1 Investigated how eco-accounting system influence sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The findings reveals that 314 respondents' responses were analyzed to obtain a correlation coefficient (r) of .726 which implies a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system practice will result to an increase sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises. The r^2 is 0.527, therefore the variation in sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is 0.527×100 is 52.7 %. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 52.7%. The findings of this study corroborated the findings of Hassan (2019) that Sales volume performance is the increases in the volume of entity revenue generated by an entity over a specific time. Sales volume performance is an increase in price of commodities and sales of more commodities or goods and services. Improving performance of sale volume is achieved by putting good marketing strategies of products and services to increase awareness and preference for advertised products and services to the competing products. It is therefore pertinent for entrepreneurs to properly device means of advertising their products and services to increase sales volume to continue operation in business as low sales volume and patronage declines profit margin of companies.

The result from Hypothesis 1 test of significance of Pearson Product moment correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and the volume of sales among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State revealed a probability value (p-value) or sig of .000 at 0.05 level of significance with 312 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, ($r(312) = .726$, $p < 0.05$) implying that there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting system and sales volume among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Thus, both groups were in agreement that eco-accounting system influences sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises.

Research Question 2 Investigated how eco-accounting system influence profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The findings revealed that 314 respondents' responses were analyzed to obtain a correlation coefficient of .800, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive strong correlation coefficient of .800 profitability among small and medium scale enterprises implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase in profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The r^2 obtained is 0.64, therefore, the variation in profitability of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is 0.64×100 is 64%. This means that, the influence of eco-accounting system on profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 64%. The findings of the study corroborated the findings of Charles (2021) that profitability performance is the measurement of company's profit efficiency that is calculated as total revenue minus total expenses and appears on the income statement of an enterprise. Profit is an absolute number determined by the amount of income or revenue above the costs or expenses an enterprise incurs.

The results from the Hypothesis 2 test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State revealed a probability value (p-value) or sig is .000 at 0.05 level of significance with 312 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, ($r(312) =$

.676, $p < 0.05$). This means that there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting system and profitability among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Thus, both groups were in agreement that eco-accounting system influences profitability of small and medium scale enterprises.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Eco-accounting system is required by all owners and managers of small and medium scale enterprises in their businesses for successful and continuous operations in Bayelsa State as it helps entrepreneurs to enhance increase sales volume, maximize and optimize profit in their respective entities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the study recommended the following:

1. That all existing and intending entrepreneurs should carry out eco-accounting system before kick starting a business venture to avert the problem of decline sales volume, profit margin and business cessation as an increase eco-accounting system practice will result to an increase sales volume and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.
2. All entrepreneurs should conduct eco-accounting system to improve productivity, reduce waste and costs of production of goods and services, improve quality of products free of defect to ensure that enterprise' products give good value for money, and use digital marketing devices such as electronic mails (E-Mails), WhatsApp, Facebook, World wide web sites, Social media, Mass media platforms, search engine such as Google, Ask, Chrome etc to advertise and sale of enterprise' goods and services to avert decline of sales volume and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.
3. Government should make the Bayelsa State business environment a safe place for businesses by unifying taxation policies to reduce the excessive multiple taxes paid by enterprises and provide constant electricity power supply to reduce the huge sums of money spent on the purchase of petrol used for generators that negatively affects the profits margin of small and medium scale enterprises to avert business cessation.

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